

STUDIES ON RANCIDITY OF BUTTERFAT. PART VII.
INFLUENCE OF WATER AND HUMIDITY
ON RANCIDITY

BY S. MUKHERJEE

The effect of increased humidity is to enhance the rate of hydrolytic rancidity of the fat. It has been found that oxidative rancidity is retarded at very high humidities, viz., 50-100%.

It has been a common observation that oils and fats are hydrolysed in contact with moisture, and early investigators generally attributed to water the property of accelerating the development of rancidity in fats, and some even believed its presence essential for the process. It was, however, shown by later workers in the field that moisture, though increased enzymatic and microbial spoilage, under certain circumstances retarded rancidity as judged by odour and taste. Rancidity appears much more readily in dry samples of milk-powder than in those containing 2-3% of water (Holm, Wright and Greenbank, *J. Dairy Sci.*, 1927, 10, 33). It was also demonstrated that with mixtures of cod-liver oil and milk-powder, addition of 10% of water greatly delayed the development of "tallowy" flavour (Anderegg and Nelson, *Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1926, 18, 620). With pure fats, it has also been observed (Greenbank and Holm, *ibid.*, 1924, 16, 598) that water increased the duration of the induction period of butterfat at 95° though most recent investigations failed to detect any influence on the induction period of lard at 50° (French, Olcott and Mattill, *ibid.*, 1935, 27, 724). Lea ("Rancidity in Edible Fats", Chem. Pub. Co., p. 184) reports that films of lard suspended over water have been found to oxidise less rapidly than similar films suspended over concentrated H₂SO₄.

It has been established by the author in a previous paper (Part IV, this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 557) that the influence of water consists essentially in causing an increased hydrolysis of the glycerides. In this paper the effect of storage of butterfat at 37° at different relative humidity has been studied. If the fat contains much water, the humidity of the atmosphere will be of less importance. Hence in the present study anhydrous butterfat has been used throughout.

EXPERIMENTAL

The samples were kept stored in small pyrex glass beakers kept in desiccators over H₂SO₄ of different concentrations so as to give the following relative humidities: 25%, 35%, 50%, 65%, 75%, 90% and finally 100% by storing over water in a desiccator. The acid concentrations were determined graphically from the table given by Willson (*Ind. Eng. Chem.*, 1921, 13, 329) correlating the strength of H₂SO₄ and relative humidities at different temperatures.

The experimental results are shown in Table I, where progress of rancidity has been determined by acid and peroxide values.

TABLE I
The effect of atmospheric humidity on hydrolysis and oxidation of butterfat at 37°.

Expt. No.	Relative humidity.	Acid and peroxide values after											
		15 days.		30 days.		45 days.		60 days.		90 days.			
		A.V.	P.V.	A.V.	P.V.	A.V.	P.V.	A.V.	P.V.	A.V.	P.V.		
1	25%	0.04	0.0	0.08	1.24	0.36	1.58	0.43	6.98	1.03	10.3		
2	35	0.06	0.0	0.03	1.17	0.40	1.70	0.52	6.14	1.21	8.0		
3	50	0.06	0.0	0.09	0.63	0.43	1.28	0.73	3.3	1.47	9.7		
4	65	0.06	0.0	0.09	1.06	0.43	1.70	0.74	7.7	1.68	12.4		
5	75	0.06	0.0	0.09	1.06	0.43	1.30	0.74	3.34	1.70	7.2		
6	90	0.09	0.0	0.10	0.74	0.47	1.00	0.94	1.46	1.90	5.7		
7	100	0.13	0.0	0.18	0.44	0.76	0.76	1.10	0.86	2.25	2.0		
8	Control (dry)	0.0	0.05	0.05	0.20	0.24	1.0	0.34	2.3	0.50	9.0		
9	Control (moisture)	0.2	0.14	0.43	0.30	0.70	2.4	1.3	3.0	2.0	18.0		

The results of these experiments are shown graphically in Figs. 1 and 2.

FIG. 1
Effect of atmospheric humidity on hydrolysis.

FIG. 2
Oxidation at 37° at diff. relative humidities.

It is evident that anhydrous fat samples, when kept in humid atmosphere, undergo hydrolytic rancidity, the degree of which increases with increase in atmospheric humidity; the effect is maximum at 90-100% humidity. Oxidation is also seen to proceed at a rate faster than the control sample in the samples 1-4. The rate of development of oxidative rancidity, as indicated by peroxide formation, is, however, slower at very high humidities (Expts. 6 and 7) than the control sample. This may tentatively be explained as follows.

The amount of moisture available at the surface of a fat sample depends on the water content of the latter and on the humidity and rate of movement of air. If the water content of the fat is nil, humidity will play the prominent role in the development of hydrolytic rancidity. In such cases it may be assumed that rancidity will develop by diffusion of moisture and oxygen from the surface to the interior of the fat, the rate of which will depend on their respective concentrations. In this case probably both oxygen and moisture are competing for the surface of the fat, and it is highly probable that at very high humidities the rate of diffusion of moisture into the fat is greater than that of oxygen, with the ultimate result that the rate of oxidation is slower at higher relative humidity (cf. experiments 6 and 7). The most reasonable conclusion to be drawn from the data is that water probably has a slightly retarding effect on the rate of absorption of oxygen by pure fats.